

2,2',-Bipyridine and 1,10-Phenanthroline Complexes of Lanthanide(III) Trifluoroacetates

SUDHINDRA N. MISRA* and MEGH SINGH**

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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The syntheses and characterization of lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetate complexes with 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline are reported. Lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetates yield compounds of the type $\text{Ln}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ or phen with 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline. Their properties and structures have been studied using chemical analyses, electronic and infrared spectra. Thermal analysis of a few complexes have also been done. The infrared data show that the trifluoroacetate group acts as a bidentate ligand making the coordination number of lanthanide eight.

FILL prepared $\text{Nd}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{AlCl}_3$ and $\text{Nd}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{ZrCl}_4$ and suggested the possible use of these as laser materials in laser technology¹. This prompted us to examine the structural characteristics of phenanthroline and bipyridine adducts of lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetate.

Experimental

Synthesis of complexes: Triquo lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetates (1 m mole) were dissolved in a mixture of ethyl acetate (10 ml) and benzene (30 ml) and the solutions were refluxed for 5-10 min. A solution of 2,2'-bipyridine or 1,10-phenanthroline (1.5 m mole) in benzene was added slowly to the above solutions. This led to the separation of microcrystalline solids. The reaction mixtures were refluxed for 15 min and the solids were filtered, washed with hot benzene and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Electronic spectral measurements of the complexes were carried out in dimethyl formamide on Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer.

The ir spectra in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} were run on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The far ir spectra in the region 650-10 cm^{-1} were recorded using a Polytec FIR-30 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. TGA of the complexes were carried out in air on Stanton AD-2 thermobalance with the rate of heating 4° min^{-1} . The metal contents of the complexes were determined by oxalate-oxide method. C, H and N analyses were carried out at micro analytical laboratory, Punjab University, Chandigarh.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results of the complexes (Table 1) conform to the general formula $\text{Ln}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{bipy}$ or phen . The complexes are soluble in ethanol and dimethyl formamide but insoluble in water, contrary to the highly soluble nature of lanthanide trifluoroacetates. This indicates a probable increases of covalent character in the complexes on introduction of bipyridine or phenanthroline upto the coordination sphere.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SOME SPECTRAL DATA FOR LANTHANIDE TRIFLUOROACETATE, BIPYRIDINE OR PHENANTHROLINE ADDUCTS

Compound	Analysis% ; Found (Calcd.)				β	$\delta(\%)$
	Metal	N	C	H		
$\text{Pr}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	22.09	4.37	30.20	1.20	0.9930	+ 0.7049
	(22.15)	(4.40)	(30.21)	(1.26)		
$\text{Nd}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	22.52	4.36	30.01	1.23	1.0085	- 0.8426
	(22.55)	(4.38)	(30.05)	(1.26)		
$\text{Sm}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$	28.20	4.28	29.65	1.21	1.0160	- 1.5742
	(23.29)	(4.33)	(29.76)	(1.24)		
$\text{Pr}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$	21.20	4.12	32.67	1.20	0.9697	+ 3.1247
	(21.34)	(4.24)	(32.74)	(1.22)		
$\text{Nd}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$	21.68	4.10	32.49	1.21	0.9945	+ 0.5530
	(21.74)	(4.22)	(32.58)	(1.21)		
$\text{Sm}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$	22.35	4.12	32.21	1.20	1.0037	- 0.3686
	(22.45)	(4.18)	(32.28)	(1.20)		

$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$ = 2,2'-bipyridine and $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3$ = 1,10-phenanthroline.

** Present address : Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 022.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF BIPYRIDINE AND PHENANTHROLINE COMPLEXES OF LANTHANON(III) TRIFLUOROACETATES

Bipyridine	Pr(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , bipy	Nd(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , bipy	Sm(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , bipy	Phenanthroline	Pr(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , phen	Nd(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , phen	Sm(CF ₃ COO) ₃ , phen	Assignments
	1640vs	1655vs 1645vs	1650s		1655vs	1650vs	1640	ν _{as} COO ⁻
1578s	1595s	1595m	1592mw	1584m	1590m	1605m	1605m	νC=C
1552s	1565m	1570m	1575m	1558m	1578w	1582m	1590mn	νC=N
			1560w	1505m	1515m	1518m	1520m	
1450vs	1470s	1460s	1450s		1460s	1430ms	1440m	ν _s COO ⁻
1425s	1440m	1440m	1440m	1445w	1455sh			
	1420w	1410w	1425w	1428s	1430w			νC-C-O
	1200	1205sh				1420w	1420vw	ν _{as} CF ₃
	1150vs	1195vs	1190		1200	1200vs	1200	
1140w		1140vs	1136vs	1197m	1145vs	1150	1150vs	ν _{as} CF ₃ + bipy or phen
1080ms	1075w	1080w	1070w	1092m	1100m	1105m	1115mw	
992s	1015vs	1015s	1005ms	-	-	-	-	Ring breathing
975sh	975m	975w	975m	-	-	-	-	satellite
890ms	890w	900w	900w	-	-	-	-	peak
				850m	862m	865m	855s	Ring breathing
	840s	840ms	830m		842ms	845s	852s	ν _s O-C
	800s	795ms	785ms		765s	798s	805s	ν _s O-F ₃
755s	700m	765ms	785ms	775ms	778m	778m	780m	bipy or phen
	760s	765ms	760ms	785ms	730s	790ms	790s	
	740sh							
	722s	728ms	725m		720s	722s	720s	O-COO in plane bending
655m	650m	650w	648s	-	640ms	640m	650m	
	645s	648s						
624vw	630m	625w	630ms	620w	628m	630m	630w	CF ₃ asym. bending
624vw	600s	600m	595m	-	602s	605s	610vs	CF ₃ sym. bending
	520s	520m	510m	-	550m	545m	530ms	νM-O
	470m	470m	465m		470m	475m	460m	νM-O
	450m	450m	445w		455w	450w	445m	νM-O
404s	420m	420w	428s	404m	425s	425ms	425m	bipy or phen +
	410m	415m	412m		422m	420m	420m	C-O-F ₃ in plane rock
								νM-O
	380w	380w	375w		385w	380m	375m	νM-O
	380w	385m	390w		326w	390w	390w	
	280s	280s	209s					
	268mw	270m	280s					νM-N
	248m	250m	230m					
	230s	245ms	215s					
	-	-	-	257w	270m	270ms	275m	phen
	-	-	-	240m	240w	245m	240w	phen
	-	-	-		197s	200s	205s	νM-N
164s	150m	155m						
	145w	148ms	148s	146m	144s	144m	148m	bipy or phen
				116s	116s	117m	110m	bipy
92m	-	-	-	89m	-	-	-	
	70s	70s	72s		76ms	76ms	80ms	
	60s	60s	60s		60s	60s	60s	
	46m	45m	47s		42m	43ms	43ms	
	35	35ms	36ms		-	-	-	
	25m	25w	25m		26s	26s	26s	

Thermal decomposition studies of Pr(TFA)₃.bipy and Pr(TFA)₃.phen reveal that the compounds remain unchanged upto ~200° beyond which they undergo slow decomposition upto ~240°. Thereafter, the decomposition rate increases considerably indicating the removal of the respective ligand, leaving anhydrous Pr(TFA)₃ at ~320°. The plateau in the thermal graph was not quite horizontal, suggesting that a slow decomposition of Pr(TFA)₃ was taking place simultaneously. The decomposition pattern beyond 320° is just the same as observed for Pr(TFA)₃. The final black powder

obtained at ~980° was analysed and found to be an equimolar mixture of PrOF and Pr₆O₁₁.

Electronic spectra : The uv spectrum of bipyridine shows two peaks at 280 and 238 nm while that of phenanthroline shows three peaks at 290, 265, 226 nm (π-π*)³. On complexation, these peaks are usually found to shift towards higher wave lengths and sometimes undergo splitting. The bipyridine complexes show two bands at 295 and 263 nm, which are due to internal π-π* transition of the ligands shifted towards higher wave length (red shift) due to coordination with the metal

ions⁴⁻⁶. The bands below 250 nm of both the ligands could not be resolved by our instrument. The comparison of the uv spectra of the ligands and their lanthanide complexes shows that no new band appears on complexation. This suggests that the charge transfer bands do not appear in the region studied (250-350 nm). The f-f transitions of lanthanide trifluoroacetates are unaffected by complexation with these ligands. Thus, the bipyridine and phenanthroline complexes of lanthanide trifluoroacetates exhibit colour characteristic of parent lanthanide ion. The oscillator strengths of the normal f→f transitions of these complexes were found to be slightly greater⁷ than those measured for corresponding aquo cation⁸, whereas the oscillator strengths of the hypersensitive bands were two times greater than the corresponding bands in the aquo ions. The position of absorption band in these complexes shift towards lower energy as compared to that in aquo ion. This is due to the expansion of the metal orbital radius resulting in the lowering of interelectronic repulsion parameter (nephelauxetic effect) represented by the nephelauxetic ratio (β), a measure of metal-ligand covalent bonding⁹⁻¹².

The value of β is less than unity and the +ve value of percentage covalency parameter (δ) indicates that there is some covalency in the metal ligand as compared to the corresponding aquo ion.

Infrared spectra : The band assignments of the spectra are based upon infrared studies of trifluoroacetic acid¹³, sodium trifluoroacetate¹⁴, lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetate¹⁵ and heterocyclic ligand¹⁶. Infrared spectra of the complexes (Table 2) are not noticeably different from those of lanthanide trifluoroacetate but certain characteristic changes have been noted, particularly with respect to ring deformation mode of heterocyclic ligand^{16,17}. The complexes of bipyridine and phenanthroline exhibit varied pattern of splitting and sometimes shifts of ligand bands, apart from intensity changes in them, as an indication of coordination of the ligand to the metal. In the free bipy molecule, strong interaction between C=C and C=N vibrations give rise to two groups of doublets (1578, 1552 and 1450, 1415 cm⁻¹). These bands undergo remarkable changes due to coordination and new bands are found to appear in the spectra of complexes at ~1595 and ~1565 cm⁻¹ confirming the coordinating nature of bipyridine ligand. The 404 cm⁻¹ band of bipy or phen (C-C out of plane bending) shifts to higher frequency and splits into two components, again confirming the coordination of bipy or phen ligand to lanthanide^{18,19}.

It has been shown²⁰⁻²² that the variation of the TFA group vibrations may be attributed to the nature of coordination of trifluoroacetate group to metal (monodentate, bidentate or bridging).

The lanthanon trifluoroacetates show bands at ~1650 and 1450 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed,

respectively, to the asymmetric $\nu_{as}COO^-$ and ν_sCOO^- stretching frequencies of the trifluoroacetate group. In lanthanon trifluoroacetates, $\nu_{as}COO^-$ decreases and ν_sCOO^- increases from the corresponding values for sodium analogue¹⁴, indicating the bidentate structure for lanthanon trifluoroacetate¹⁵. The lanthanon trifluoroacetate complexes of bipy and phen show $\nu_{as}COO^-$ band at ~1655 cm⁻¹ and ν_sCOO^- at ~1460 cm⁻¹. Thus the difference between the two COO⁻ frequencies [$\Delta\nu = (\nu_{as}COO^- - \nu_sCOO^-)$] of lanthanon trifluoroacetates and their bipy and phen complexes is very similar. The close similarity in the magnitude of $\Delta\nu$ for lanthanon trifluoroacetate and its bipy and phen complexes confirms the bidentate attachment of the trifluoroacetate group to metal. It has been suggested on Spinner's argument¹⁴ that there is considerable degree of mixing of the C-C stretching vibration with the low frequency COO⁻ stretching (symmetric stretching). The C-C stretching mode is better described as a mixture of symmetric and asymmetric -O-C-C stretching mode, and thus the vibration is expected to be sensitive to the coordination of the COO⁻ group. It has been postulated that there is a release of electrons from the fluorine and oxygen atoms into π -molecular orbitals delocalized over the whole molecule and that this effect is promoted when COO⁻ group is involved in bidentate coordination.

In all the complexes only two bands are observed in the 1220-1135 cm⁻¹ region, which are assigned to the $\nu_{as}CF_3$ stretching vibrations. The absence of the third CF₃ band again supports the bidentate attachment of trifluoroacetate group rather than the monodentate where all the three $\nu_{as}CF_3$ are present²².

There was no change in the frequencies of the CF₃ deformation modes between lanthanon trifluoroacetate and their bipy and phen complexes. The higher one can be assigned to asymmetric while the lower one to symmetric mode. This also confirms the bidentate coordination of trifluoroacetate group. In the monodentate attachment, CF₃ deformations must occur at lower frequencies due to the C-C single bond character.

Experimental studies²³⁻²⁵ of rare earth complexes have revealed that vibrations appearing in the region 500-300 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to M-O stretching vibrations. These bands have been considered to contain M-O stretching character to a varying degree because of stronger coupling between various vibrational modes. The bands occurring at the lower end will have least coupling interferences as they are known to exhibit the maximum sensitivity to the metal.

The far infrared spectra of these complexes were recorded where $\nu(M-N)$ and metal sensitive vibrations appear. It has been difficult, however, to assign $\nu(M-N)$ empirically since several ligand vibrations also appear in the same frequency region. Bipy itself does not absorb in the region

300-200 cm^{-1} but we observed four strong absorption bands in this region in the complexes. These have been assigned to M-N ligand vibrations. This most probably indicates that M-N bond in Pr, Nd and Sm analogue shows an ascending trend. Nakamoto *et al*²⁶ explained the shift to higher frequency in complexes in terms of stronger M-N bond. On the same lines we can suggest that the M-N bond becomes more stable with the rise of atomic number.

The absorption pattern in the region 250-175 cm^{-1} in phen complexes is a bit more complicated since phen itself absorbs in this region. Several strong to medium bands are observed in the 250-175 cm^{-1} . The strongest band $\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed a gradual increase with the rise in atomic number. These bands can be assigned to M-N vibrations which are absent in phen. The far ir spectra between 200-10 cm^{-1} of both the complexes is extremely difficult to interpret because several strong to medium bands appeared in this region which may be lattice vibrations as well as a number of coupling modes. Also, N-M-N bonding vibrations might be expected to occur in this region.

Thus the lanthanide(III) trifluoroacetate bipy or phen complexes can be represented as $\text{Ln}(\text{CF}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{N} \end{array} \right)$ with a coordination number of eight for the metal ion.

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